

**DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AS A PRIORITY DIRECTION IN THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT
OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION**

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Abstract

The article analyzes the justification of the need to apply digital technologies in this sector in order to create positive conditions for the creation of a digital economy in the agricultural sector. The article also argues that the application of digital technologies is an integral part of the future development of the country's agricultural production. From this point of view, four main directions (technical and technological improvement, economic growth, increase of environmental cleanliness and personnel potential) in which the digitization of the economy of the agricultural sector will increase the competitiveness of the agricultural sector are analyzed. The article also reflects the factors that hinder the formation of the digital economy in the agricultural sector. These factors are divided into external and internal factors. Within the framework of external factors, the natural basis of agriculture, deficiencies in the regulatory and legal framework, weak infrastructure and financial support for digitization are emphasized. Production, economic and other factors conditioned by the economic activity of the enterprise are attributed to internal factors. It is proposed to activate state support for the use of digital technologies in agricultural production to equalize the established restrictions. For this, depending on the type of product, both the gradual orientation of the producers from the modernization of the existing technical and technological processes to the use of digitization elements, and the parallel stimulation of the modernization of the existing production facilities and the application of digital technologies were proposed.

Keywords: digital economy, agriculture, digital technologies.

Introduction. The need to protect and develop the competitive advantages of all sectors of the national economy is one of the main problems. The opportunity to use raw material advantages begins to complement itself and prompts to apply other, advanced methods of farming. In this case, the main direction is to focus on long-term goals that will strengthen the position of our Republic in the world economy for many years (Abdulayev M. (2022)).

Despite the fact that agriculture is one of the most dynamically developing areas in the last few years, digitalization issues are the most relevant for it. It is agriculture, due to its characteristics, that is far from the use of modern IT technologies and the latest economic management tools. The lagging behind of agriculture in the development of the digital economy is also confirmed by the statistics of the application of innovative technologies to the production process, which gives agricultural production an outsider position compared to other industries (Jamilzade Sh.V. (2020)). With all this, raising the economic efficiency of agriculture to a competitive level in terms of the world market is impossible without improving and developing the main creative force of the agrarian economy, its potential re-

serve. The development of the agricultural sector is objectively determined by the need to create conditions for the creation of a new digital economy that allows providing the population with food products of the appropriate quality and quantity (Golovenchik G.G. (2019)).

The purpose of the study. To determine the level of digitization in agriculture and the development prospects of the digital economy. Group the factors that hinder the implementation of digital technologies and propose measures to strengthen this process in agricultural production.

Material and research methods.

The theoretical basis of the presented research was the development of local and foreign authors in the field of studying the principles and foundations of the formation of the digital economy, as well as the use of advanced IT technologies in the field of production and economic relations. agricultural producers. The official data of the Republic and regional statistical bodies, the Ministry of Agriculture, the Regional Departments of Agriculture, as well as the observations and researches of individual scientists were used as analytical material.

During the research, systematic and logical approaches were involved, monographic, economic-statistical, as well as expert assessment and scientific abstraction method were used as research methods.

Research findings and discussion.

It should be noted that the main subjects of economic relations in order to strengthen the process of applying digital economy elements to agriculture are state institutions and agricultural producers. Based on the currently formed economic structure of agriculture, it is possible to distinguish agricultural organizations, households, peasant (farmer) farms (Balayev R.A. (2020)).

Surveying of agricultural fields from drones, analysis of agrochemical composition of soils using satellite images, programmable agricultural machinery connected to sensors in the soil are already the reality of the industry today, and this is only a small part of the innovative developments currently presented (Jamilzade Sh.V.). However, penetration of digital technologies in rural areas is extremely low. It is a pity that the founders, owners, owners pay little attention to information technologies, because the transition of Russian agricultural production to digital technologies is important for ensuring the conditions for the sustainable economic development of all agriculture (Golovenchik G.G. (2019)).

It is proposed to classify the factors hindering the formation of the digital economy in agriculture as external and internal. External factors include:

- the natural and biological basis of agriculture;
- shortcomings of legislative and regulatory regulation (for example, the confidentiality of some aerial photography data, the lack of clear rules for the use of drones);
- underdeveloped infrastructure (mediation, legal, banking and other services) that ensures the promotion and application of digital technologies;
- lack of development of the market of digital technologies;
- lack of financial support from the state (for example, the difficulty of obtaining state subsidies for the implementation of digital technologies for precision agriculture).

Among the internal factors, it is necessary to mention production, economy and others related to the economic activity of the enterprise.

Production factors can be formulated as difficulties in predicting final results due to high production risks in agricultural production; the uncertainty of the timing of the application process of digital technologies; dependence of the production process on natural and biological factors (Abdullayev M. (2022)).

The composition of economic factors includes uneven formation of reserves of own financial resources; high price; the duration of the payback periods of digital technologies; lack of information about sales markets; existence of economic risks; low consumer demand for digital technologies for agriculture.

Factors related to the enterprise's economic activity include a lack of qualified personnel; lack of opportunities to attract investors, scientific organizations and others (Balayev R.A. (2020)).

How to ensure that new digital developments reach agricultural producers remains an open question.

In this regard, it is proposed to strengthen state support for the application and use of digital technologies in agricultural production. For this, it makes sense to focus more on stimulating agricultural producers to implement digital innovations, and at the same time to stop work on the invention and creation of these technologies. State support should be divided into two areas.

First, it should be related to the production of products (cereals, sunflowers, poultry, etc.) that have already reached the level of self-sufficiency in the country. Here, the main focus should be directed to the modernization of the existing technical and technological means of production of the manufacturer to the use of digitization elements based on the expansion of foreign trade and export activities. The second direction should be related to the production of agricultural products that do not have a minimum sufficient value to ensure food independence. In such a case, it is necessary to focus on the domestic market and carry out modernization of existing production capacities and parallel development of digitalization (Entin V. L. (2017)).

Results.

It should be noted that digitalization is beginning to come to the agrarian sector and is one of the main vectors of its development. The problem facing the industry and what interests developers, and most importantly, professionals involved in the implementation of developments in practice, is how they will be integrated. Such integration is impossible without the participation of artificial intelligence, without the systematization of large databases, since their volume is growing exponentially. At the same time, I would like to hope that in the near future many farmers in our country will be able to use the potential of digitalization to achieve the conditions of sustainable economic growth of agricultural production.

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